

Multi-model Deep Learning approach for segmentation of teeth and periapical pathology on Orthopantomograms

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- Ethical exemption letter associated with this study has been uploaded.

Abstract:

Introduction: The fields of medicine and dentistry are beginning to integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) in diagnostics. This may reduce subjectivity and improved accuracy of diagnoses and treatment planning. Current evidence on pathology detection on Orthopantomograms (OPGs) indicates the presence or absence of disease in the entire radiographic image, with little evidence of relation of periapical pathology to the causative tooth.

Objective: To develop a Deep Learning (DL) AI model for the segmentation of periapical pathology and its relation to teeth on OPGs.

Methodology: 250 OPGs were manually annotated by subject experts to lay down the ground truth for training AI algorithms on segmentation of periapical pathology. Two approaches were used for lesion detection: multi-models 1 and 2, utilizing U-net and Mask RCNN algorithms, respectively. The resulting segmented lesions generated on the testing dataset were superimposed with results of teeth segmentation and numbering algorithms trained separately to relate lesions to causative teeth. Hence, both multi-model approaches related periapical pathology to the causative teeth on OPG.

Results: The performance metrics of lesion segmentation carried out by U-net are as follows: accuracy=98.1%, precision=84.5%, re-call=80.3%, F-1 score=82.2%, dice index=75.2%, and IoU=67.6%. Mask RCNN carried out lesion segmentation with an accuracy of 46.7%, precision of 80.6%, recall of 55%, and F-1 score of 63.1%.

Conclusion: In this study, the multi-model approach successfully related periapical pathology to the causative tooth on OPGs. However, U-net outperformed Mask RCNN in the tasks performed, suggesting that U-net will remain standard for medical image segmentation tasks. Further training

of the models on other findings and an increased number of images will lead to automation of the dental diagnostic workflow.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, Machine Learning, Dentistry, Imaging, Neural Networks, Convolutional Neural Network, Intraoral Radiography, Periapical Periodontitis

Introduction:

Orthopantomograms (OPGs) are the most common imaging modality, used for analysis of the dentition and related anatomy for a complete dental evaluation.¹ They provide a panoramic view of teeth, maxilla, mandible, maxillary sinuses, temporomandibular joints, etc.¹ Some radiographic findings are incidental on OPG especially if the patient is asymptomatic thus, indicating when further area-specific evaluation is needed.² An example is periapical pathology, caused by apical periodontitis, which presents as a radiolucent area around the apices of teeth.³ The detection of periapical pathology on OPG is 77% sensitive and 95% specific, therefore when detected, a periapical radiograph can be obtained for a more detailed examination.⁴ Hence, OPG has good overall diagnostic discriminatory ability and is employed in daily clinical practice as a screening tool.^{5,6}

Computer Vision (CV) is a field AI that allows computers to derive meaningful information from images, with its consequent application to solve problems.^{7,8} Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are the algorithms of choice when applying AI techniques on images.^{9,10} CNNs are robust at a variety of CV tasks, including object detection, segmentation and classification (**figure 1**).^{10,11} These tasks can be applied to radiographs for detection of normal anatomy as well as pathology for developing an automated clinical decision support system. Therefore, the main objective of our research is to train AI to identify and list all possible findings on OPGs, including normal and pathological conditions. The first step towards this goal was to train an AI model to perform teeth segmentation and numbering tasks, details of which can be found in the cited text.¹² In this paper, we describe the second step towards automation, which involves the detection of periapical pathology and its relation to teeth on OPGs. Once adequately trained this tool will screen for periapical pathology and alert clinicians to investigate possibly diseased teeth with further area-

specific radiographs as well as clinical tests. Previous literature has described the use of AI for detecting periapical pathology on radiographs, but they only detect the presence or absence of disease in the entire radiograph without relating it to relevant anatomical structure.^{2, 13}

This paper explains an extension of our previous work¹² and two approaches were used to detect and relate periapical pathology to specific teeth on OPGs. In the future, expansion of this work will lead to the development of an AI-based diagnostic software that will improve overall efficiency of the dental diagnostic workflow.

Methodology:

This study was conducted at Aga Khan University Hospital (AKUH), Karachi, Pakistan from May 2022 to August 2022. OPGs were retrieved from the radiographic database of dental clinics after obtaining exemption from the ethics review committee (2022-8083-23090) of the institution. All OPGs taken between the mentioned time period were reviewed and only those fulfilling the inclusion criteria were utilized in the study. OPGs from an open-sourced dataset TUFTS Dental Database (TDD) were also used to train and test the algorithms.¹⁴ The sample size for training the algorithm was determined arbitrarily and training was terminated when the algorithms reached near saturation. OPGs were selected via non-probability purposive sampling technique according to the set inclusion and exclusion criteria as follows.

Inclusion criteria:

- Good quality OPGs
- Teeth with closed apices
- Fully erupted permanent dentition
- Periapical pathology associated with one or more teeth

Exclusion criteria:

OPGs with:

- Artifacts
- Impacted teeth
- Supernumerary teeth
- Deciduous teeth
- Orthodontic appliances, titanium plates and wires
- Generalized root resorption post orthodontic treatment

OPGs obtained from locally sourced dataset were scanned by Orthophos XG 3-D (Dentsply Sirona GmbH, Bensheim, Deutschland) operated at 60-90 kV and 3-16 mA; with the dimensions of 2440x1292 pixels, captured in gray level. The OPGs were downloaded from SIDEXIS XG 2.63 software in Portable Network Graphics (PNG) format from the image database. The OPGs were anonymized, and patient metadata was not made available. All OPGs were kept in a database, which was password protected and only accessible to the authors of this study. OPGs from TDD were also utilized; the owners of this dataset provided masks to be employed in training, however for the purpose of this study we carried out our own annotations to maintain accuracy and uniformity in annotations.¹⁴

Dataset Annotation:

The images comprising the dataset were in two formats, PNG for locally sourced dataset, and Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG) for TDD. A segmentation map for every tooth was created manually via polygons using the Labelme software which was downloaded from GitHub.¹⁵ Each

of the 250 radiographs were labelled and annotations were generated in JSON format to be used for training.

Every OPG was annotated for three tasks as shown in **figure 2**, namely, individual teeth segmentation according to the class (molar, premolar, etc) and teeth numbers using bounding boxes according to the Fédération Dentaire Internationale (FDI) numbering system (18, 17, 16, etc). These formed the ground truth for training algorithms for teeth segmentation and teeth numbering tasks. The same cohort of 250 OPGs was also annotated for periapical pathology separately using the same software. The annotations were carried out denoting lesions at apices of teeth by zooming in the OPGs by 200% for better visualization (**figure 2**). This separate annotated dataset formed the ground truth for training algorithms for lesion segmentation task.

All annotations were carried out by two investigators of this study: a postgraduate student and a specialist endodontist. The annotations by the first investigator were checked by the second investigator and vice versa, any conflicts in the annotations were resolved via discussion. All investigators were calibrated on the use of the software before beginning the annotation process. The performance of all algorithms was evaluated using the testing dataset after training was complete. This study was performed in accordance with the Artificial intelligence in dental research checklist by Schwendicke *et al*; the following narrative explains two techniques utilized by authors to carry out lesion segmentation and consequently relate it to the causative tooth on OPG.¹⁵ The following narrative describes the use of two multi-models for relating periapical pathology to causative teeth.

Multi-model 1:

Three CNNs were used in this approach for the segmentation and numbering of all teeth as well as segmentation of periapical pathology on OPGs. Two CNNs (U-net and Faster RCNN) were

previously trained for teeth segmentation and numbering¹² (**figure 3**) additionally, another U-net was trained on periapical pathology detection.¹⁶ The three algorithms were ran in parallel (**figure 3**) and the results of each were super imposed via python code written specifically for the purpose of superimposition. The details of the three algorithms are as follows:

1. U-net **A**: Teeth segmentation algorithm previously trained (further trained on 250 OPGs)
2. Faster RCNN: Teeth numbering algorithm previously trained (further trained on 250 OPGs)
3. U-net **B**: Lesion segmentation algorithm

The basic U-net algorithm employed, an in-depth explanation of the workings of the algorithms is beyond the scope of this paper and can be found elsewhere.¹⁷

Before training, each radiograph was resized from the original dimensions of 2440×1292 pixels to 512×512 pixels to account for the limited computational resources. The training was carried out on GoogleColabPro, with random initialization of parameters.¹⁸

The previously trained algorithms, U-net **A** and Faster RCNN were further trained and tested on 250 annotated images with the methodology as described in the previous paper (**figure 3**).¹² Additionally, U-net **B** algorithm was trained and tested on the same set 250 OPGs using similar parameters as the previous algorithms, for lesion detection task.¹² However, complete OPGs were not used for training this algorithm, instead the bounding boxes generated from Faster RCNN formed the training dataset for this algorithm. To ensure that lesions were captured adequately within the outlines of these boxes, the generated bounding boxes were enlarged by 100 pixels. These enlarged images formed individual tooth ‘crops’ that were used to train U-net **B**. A total of 1354 crops (from 250 OPGs) were used to train U-net **B**, the images were augmented using

techniques stated in the previous study.¹² Out of 1354 images, 1273 were used for training the algorithm, 13 for validation and 68 were used for testing the performance of the algorithm; this split was carried out randomly by the algorithm. It is important to note that out of the 1354 crops, 747 crops contained periapical lesions, out of which 230 contained lesions associated with endodontically treated teeth. This indicates that the disease prevalence in our dataset was almost 50%.

The algorithm was trained using adam optimizer with binary cross entropy loss function. It was trained for 50 epochs, with each epoch taking 160 iterations. The training process took 2.2 hours, with an average of 158.4 seconds per epoch with batch size of 8.

Since U-net **B** were trained on crops, these had to be ‘reverse mapped’ onto whole OPGs to be superimposed on the visual results of U-net **A** and Faster RCNN as shown in **figure 3** (see **table 1** for performance metrics).

Results (Multi-model 1):

The algorithms were successful in achieving the desired tasks at reasonable performance metrics. The visual results are shown in **figure 3**. Various performance metrics were used to gauge the performance of U-net **A**, U-net **B** and Faster RCNN algorithms.

The performance of the existent teeth segmentation, U-net **A** was further improved as indicated by the following performance metrics including accuracy=98.1%, precision=91.8%, re-call=93.3%, F-1 score=92.5%, dice index=90.1% and Intersection over Union (IoU)=82.1% for U-net **A**. The performance metrics of the Faster RCNN algorithm were determined using overlap accuracy=16.3 bounding boxes and classifier accuracy of labels=93.9%. This is relative to the previous performance metrics when it was trained and tested on only 50 OPGs.¹²

The performance metrics of lesion segmentation algorithm carried out by the current model, U-net **B**, are as follows: accuracy=98.1%, precision=84.5%, re-call=80.3%, F-1 score=82.2%, dice index=75.2% and IoU=67.6%.

(An explanation of the metrics can be found in the supplementary paper)

Multi-model 2:

Two Mask RCNN algorithms formed multi-model 2. These were trained on a computer equipped with Nvidia GTX-1060, a CUDA-based GPU, on Tensorflow 2.0, paired with Intel's 8th Generation Core i7 CPU and 16GB DDR4 RAM. The backbone for Mask R-CNN used in this model was ResNet50.¹⁹ The initial weights for the model were loaded from COCO dataset.²⁰ The training process was run continuously, until the marginal improvement between epochs was below the 1% threshold (**figure 5**). This multi-model comprises of two algorithms trained on 250 OPGs, randomly split into training, validation and testing datasets by the algorithms, performing the following tasks:

1. Mask RCNN **A**: Mask RCNN for teeth segmentation and numbering
2. Mask RCNN **B**: Mask RCNN for lesion segmentation

These algorithms were trained using the stochastic gradient descent optimizer with sigmoid loss function.

The teeth segmentation and numbering Mask RCNN algorithm (Mask RCNN **A**) was ran for 310 epochs, with each epoch taking 100 iterations. In addition, the data was augmented for this model to include variety as well as expand the number of examples.

The data was augmented using the following techniques:

1. Cropping and padding each side of the lesion polygons by 25%
2. Blend in Alpha channel and remove about 50% of the color
3. Flip random 50% of the images horizontally and random 50% vertically
4. Scale images from 75% to 125% of their original size
5. Rotate images between -30° and 30°
6. Sheer images by -15° to 15°

The training process took 12 hours, with an average of 135.4 seconds per epoch. The batch size for training the algorithm was 2, and the images were scaled to maximum width and height of 832 pixels. Each tooth was identified by a label, according to FDI numbering system, therefore 32 classes were used for training. All boxes generated from this algorithm were saved separately forming the ‘crops’ to train the other algorithm.

The crops generated from Mask RCNN **A** (153 in total) formed the training dataset for lesion detection Mask RCNN algorithm (Mask RCNN **B**). The Mask RCNN B algorithm was trained for 500 epochs, each running for 100 iterations. This model took 11 hours of training, with an average of 63.8 seconds per epoch. The batch size for this model was 1, while the other parameters remain similar to that of Mask RCNN A.

Once trained, both models were sequentially run to predict teeth segmentation and numbering, as well as lesions on the same test images. Both outputs are superimposed for combined feedback, such that the output from Mask RCNN A is overlapped on Mask RCNN B output with 50% transparency (**figure 4**) (see **table 1** for performance metrics).

Results (Multi-model 2):

Aside from the overall evaluation, we used Tensorboard utility, provided by TensorFlow toolkit, to measure how the models progressed over time.

The performance metrics of Mask RCNN A included an accuracy of 54.8%, precision of 100%, recall of 54.8% and F-1 score of 70.6%. Similarly, the performance metrics of Mask RCNN B included an accuracy of 46.7%, precision of 80.6%, recall of 55% and F-1 score of 63.1%.

A comparison of results based on tasks:

Tables 1 **a** and **b** compare the performance relative to the specific tasks performed. The combination of U-net **A** and Faster RCNN carry out teeth segmentation and numbering tasks with higher performance compared to Mask RCNN **A**. U-net **B** algorithm segments lesions with better performance compared to Mask RCNN **B**. In our study both U-nets outperformed the other algorithms in their respective tasks.

A direct comparison of both U-nets shows higher performance of U-net **A** (teeth segmentation) compared to U-net **B** (lesion segmentation). This is assumed to be due to the increased number of examples of ‘teeth’ on OPG compared to the fewer number of ‘lesions’ used to train the algorithms.

Both lesion segmentation algorithms U-net **B** and Mask RCNN **B** were trained on the crops generated from the preceding teeth numbering algorithms. Here the authors would like to emphasize the difference in the number of crops used for training each algorithm. While U-net **B** was trained on 1354 crops, Mask RCNN **B** was trained on only 153 crops. This vast difference was due to the different accuracies of the teeth numbering algorithms generating the crops for each algorithm. Therefore, extensive augmentation of data for Mask RCNN to account for this difference but the results of this algorithm are still relatively poor.

Discussion:

With the advancement of AI techniques in biomedical imaging, there has been an upsurge of its application in radiographic diagnosis. Among these, identification of normal anatomy and the detection of pathology has been well investigated in literature.^{11, 13} However, the relation of pathology with associated anatomy has not been explored thoroughly. Similarly, this gap has been observed in dental radiomics as well, where the association of periapical disease with teeth is not well established.^{2, 13, 21 22, 23} The localization of periapical pathology to causative tooth is a critical element of dental diagnosis. Real-life applicability can be achieved if the origin of pathology and associated anatomy is related. The detection of teeth alone or the presence/absence of pathology in an entire image carries no benefit for clinicians. From a clinical standpoint, the relation of pathology to teeth outweighs the high-performance metrics of algorithm in terms of providing better patient healthcare.

A recent systematic review by Sadr *et al.* found that DL models had acceptable accuracy for detecting lesions on periapical radiographs, OPGs and Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) images.¹³ However, the authors of the included studies did not analyze whether the disease i.e. periapical pathology was related to causative anatomy.¹³ In a study by Yuksel *et al.*, they designed a DL model that performs teeth numbering task and also recommends treatment needs of individual teeth, thus overcoming some of the shortcomings in current literature.²⁴ The main objective of this study was to develop a DL algorithm for periapical disease detection along with detection and relation teeth. Since the task was multifold, the authors designed a robust methodology including multiple algorithms. The first goal of this study was to train AI model that can perform teeth segmentation and numbering on OPGs with high accuracy which the authors have achieved.¹² In continuation with the previous work, another finding (i.e. periapical pathology) was added to the model, which resulted in segmentation of periapical pathology and

improved performance of the teeth segmentation and numbering tasks. In the execution of this task, a heterogeneous dataset of OPGs were used for training i.e., images with missing teeth, restorative and prosthetic work, carious lesions, etc. And to incorporate variation in our dataset and to improve generalizability of the models, images from TDD were also included.¹⁴

In this study, two models were trained for lesion detection, both are examples of ‘ensemble learning’.²⁵ This is the combination of multiple algorithms, usually carried out to improve accuracy of results of the individual algorithms. It includes techniques such as bagging, boosting, stacking and blending to enhance accuracy.²⁵ However, integration of visual results also comes under the umbrella of an ‘ensemble’ and results from each of the algorithms are stacked for a final result.²⁶ Alternatively, the models in our experiment can also be classified as ‘multi-model’ deep neural networks since multiple algorithms are trained independently on the same dataset to learn different representations, and generate complementary results.²⁷

For multi-model 1, we aimed to improve on our existing algorithms as well as adding another algorithm, U-net **B** for lesion detection and achieved an accuracy of 98.1%. This model comprises of three algorithms running in parallel which were consequently combined to relate periapical pathology to the causative tooth. To achieve optimal performance, each algorithm was trained to execute only one task. Since U-net **B** was trained on crops, these had to be reverse mapped back onto whole OPGs to generate an image compatible for superimposition with the other two algorithms. This multi-model used U-net algorithms which are known to specialize in image segmentation tasks and with relatively smaller datasets for training, which is adequately reflected in the results.

In an attempt to improve computational efficiency, Mask RCNN was used to reduce the number of algorithms required to achieve tasks. Mask RCNN can perform all three tasks (shown in **figure**

1) concurrently, as opposed to U-net (teeth segmentation) and Faster RCNN (teeth numbering). Multi-model 2 comprised of two similar algorithms running in series, one performing teeth segmentation and numbering (Mask RCNN **A**) and the other segmenting lesions (Mask RCNN **B**), with consequent superimposition of results. The outputs generated by Mask RCNN **A** formed the training dataset for Mask RCNN **B**, and the output of Mask RCNN **B** was reverse mapped onto whole OPGs for a consolidated result, similar to multi-model 1. The accuracy of lesion segmentation of this model, however, was only 46.7% even having utilized a more versatile algorithm. He *et al.* compared Mask R-CNN with other state-of-the-art object detection algorithms on COCO dataset and concluded that Mask R-CNN outperformed other algorithms in image segmentation.²⁸ Therefore, the authors of this study utilized the weights from a Mask RCNN algorithm pre-trained on COCO dataset, however the results are contrary.^{19, 20} This could be attributed to the fact that He *et al.* did not carry out these tasks on radiographs as was the case in this study.¹⁹ In this model, the dataset was also augmented in an attempt to improve performance but the results remained unsatisfactory. Therefore, in our experiment the U-net approach has been successful in lesion segmentation thus far.

Both lesion segmentation algorithms of multi-model 1 and 2, were trained on crops generated from their respective teeth segmentation and numbering algorithms. This was done to eliminate confounding anatomical landmarks such as mental foramen from data that can be mistaken for periapical pathology. Using crops also increased the number of images comprising the training dataset. The use of reverse-mapping technique led to the generation of composite results of both multi-models, 1 and 2.

The high performance of U-net has been consistent as evidenced by Setzer *et al* and Zheng *et al* who achieved a dice index of 67% and 74% on lesion detection on CBCT images, respectively.²⁹

³⁰ This is in comparison to the dice index score of 75.2% achieved by U-net **B** trained in this study. Bayrakdar *et al* also used U-net to detect periapical pathology on OPG with IoU of 70% using 470 images, compared to 67.6% in this study.³¹

A recent study by Fatima *et al* successfully trained a Mask RCNN for lesion detection with an accuracy of 94% however they used periapical images in their dataset.³² In comparison Mask RCNN **B** in this study achieved an accuracy of 46.7% on OPG, the low accuracy may be attributed to the lower resolution of OPG relative to periapical radiographs that can make lesion segmentation a difficult task to execute.

The strengths of this study include the use of a multi-model approach to successfully relate periapical pathology to the causative teeth. The use of a locally sourced dataset as well as TDD enhanced the diversity of the data in this study.¹³ As mentioned in the recent systematic review by Sadr *et al.*, lesions are difficult to detect especially on OPG due to their smaller size as well as poorly defined borders. Therefore, in an attempt to account for this deficiency, the OPGs were zoomed to 200% during annotation for better visualization of lesions. And crops were used rather than whole OPGs to increase the diagnostic yield of both lesion detection algorithms (U-net **B** and Mask RCNN **B**).

One of the limitations of our study, however, is the lack of general applicability of results due to the strict inclusion criteria where all OPGs included has periapical pathology. This led to the incorporation of selection bias and the number of crops with and without lesions being at almost 1:1. As mentioned previously, this indicates that the disease prevalence in our dataset is higher than that found in the general population. Therefore, further training on a dataset with disease prevalence that is reflective of the population is needed. The authors emphasize that an OPG is not diagnostic for periapical pathology and clinical presentation of these lesions could not be

accounted for due to the nature of this study. However, the detection of a periapical lesion directs the clinician to further investigate the region using area-specific radiographs and clinical testing. Furthermore, our results cannot be generalized on entire populations, for example on pediatric patients since these OPGs were excluded. Our models are at stage 2 of AI development, according to Zhang *et al.* and all the aforementioned limitations are usually addressed at stages 3 and 4 which include model deployment that the authors are working towards.³³ In the future, authors aim to further train the algorithms on current diagnostic tasks and also to train AI for detection of additional pathologies on OPG with the ultimate goal of automation. At that stage, a head-to-head comparison of AI methods with humans can also be performed to determine the actual performance of these models in real-life settings. Moreover, there is a lack of data on how AI may alter the diagnostic process and decision-making or how it may impact cost-effectiveness.³⁴ Once AI development reaches stage 4 this crucial information will be determined, and a true cost-benefit analysis of AI in healthcare will be carried out effectively.

Conclusion:

Both models were able perform teeth segmentation and numbering tasks on OPG as well as relating the pathology to causative teeth. However, U-net was consistently better at the tasks it was being trained for with 98.1% accuracy. Even though Mask RCNN is a more versatile and complex algorithm, it failed to deliver the same robustness and accuracy (46.7%) compared to U-net. Within the limitations of this study, the authors concluded that U-net may remain the algorithm of choice for medical image segmentation until a more robust algorithm proves otherwise.

(The code for both algorithms can be found using the following link:

<https://github.com/Niihhaa/lesion-detection-both-algorithms-.git>)

Legends:

Figure 1:

(a): Object detection; teeth are localized using bounding boxes

(b): Semantic segmentation; teeth are separated from the background using fluid outlines

(c): Classification; diseased and healthy teeth are classified separately

Figure 2:

(a): Unannotated, raw OPG to be annotated

(b): OPG with teeth annotated using polygons to separate each pixel of the tooth from background

(c): Periapical lesions annotated using polygons after being zoomed in for better visualization

(d): OPG with teeth annotated using bounding boxes according to the FDI numbering system

Figure 3:

(a): Teeth segmentation and numbering results of U-net **A** and Faster RCNN combined

(b): Lesion segmentation results of U-net **B**

(c): Workflow of multi-model 1 with results of all three algorithms combined

Figure 4:

(a): An unseen image ran through multi-model 2

(b): Teeth segmentation and numbering results of Mask RCNN **A**

(c): Teeth crops generated from Mask RCNN **A** formed the dataset for Mask RCNN **B**

(d): Lesion segmentation results which crops reverse mapped back to form a whole OPG

(e): Composite result of Mask RCNN **A** and Mask RCNN **B**

Table 1:

(a): Performance metrics of teeth segmentation and numbering tasks

(b): Performance metrics of lesion segmentation task

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Supplementary paper

Definitions of metrics utilized:

1. Accuracy: calculated as $Accuracy = \frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN}$ where TP is True-Positives, or the number of segments predicted correctly; FP is False-Positives, or the number of segments predicted incorrectly; FN is False-Negatives, or the number of segments not predicted.
2. Precision: tells when a model classifies a segment, how correct the class label is. It is calculated as $Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
3. Recall: tells out of all segments which existed, how many were retrieved by the model. It is computed as $Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
4. F1-score: this is the harmonic mean of Precision and recall, and gives a balanced measurement between the two. It is given as $F1 = \frac{2 * precision * recall}{precision + recall}$
5. Intersection over Union (IoU): It is an performance metric used to measure the accuracy of object detection on a particular dataset.

$$IoU = \frac{\text{Area of overlap}}{\text{Area of union}}$$

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4